

IMPORTANT FACTORS FOR DETERMINING AND PROMOTING NEW ECONOMIC RELATIONS IN THE AGRICULTURAL FIELD

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Abstract. *In this article, state regulation of agriculture, state support, state agrarian policy, opinions of economists are presented in this regard, the share of agriculture in gross added value, labor productivity is analyzed. . The main directions of the state support of agriculture in Uzbekistan, its measures are given, and the author proposed a structural scheme of the state regulation of the development of agriculture in the country.*

Keywords: *agriculture, new economic relations, state regulation, state support, state agrarian policy, labor productivity, privilege, lending and subsidizing, financial market, project.*

Introduction. State regulation of agriculture, as well as improvement of food supply to the population, maintenance of economic balance and convergence of income levels between the agricultural sector and other economic sectors, local agricultural development It is also characterized by the fact that it aims to protect the interests of producers.

Business activity in agriculture is highly risky and the income of business entities operating in the field depends on natural and climatic conditions, which shows that the income of agricultural enterprises has an unstable nature.

In addition, it should be noted that the rate of wear and tear of fixed assets in agricultural production is somewhat higher than in other sectors and industries, as they operate in unfavorable conditions.

Studying the factors that affect the effective functioning of the agricultural sector in a holistic way allows to study not only which factors have the greatest influence, but also to study the elements of the process separately from each other. This, in turn, makes it possible to clarify the essence of the problem, which seems insignificant from the outside, but is of great importance in the solution of the problem.

Today, the situation in the agricultural sector in Uzbekistan requires the active intervention of the state along the entire production chain. As mentioned above, it is necessary to study the factors affecting the process not statically, but dynamically. The nature of the factors affecting the agrarian sector is also characterized by its changeable nature, and the factors that have a positive impact on the sector may have a negative impact after a certain period of time.

Literature review. State regulation of agriculture and state agencies of various economic entities (financial and credit system institutions, agricultural machinery and equipment, fertilizer, veterinary equipment manufacturers, breeding farms) refers to achieving the efficiency of agricultural production by establishing coordinated actions (Touzard and Labarthe 2018).

As for the concept of "state support", this concept largely refers to financial calculations, that is, it reflects the quantitative expression of state regulation and public policy (Erokhin, Ivolga and Heijman 2014). It should be noted that the result of the regulatory policy of the state is reflected

in the increase in the amount of support in the form of gross transfers to agriculture from the budget, including from tax payers and consumers of agricultural products. Iadi

As for "state agrarian policy", this concept is characterized by having a more political-legal description (Binswanger, Deininger, 1997). The policy of the state in the agrarian sector envisages regulation of the sector through regulatory and legal documents. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 23.10.2019 No. PF-5853 "On approval of the strategy for the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" states that the main goal of the agrarian policy implemented by the state is to develop diversification of production, improvement of land and water relations, creation of a favorable agribusiness environment and high added value chain, support for the development of cooperative relations, wide introduction of market mechanisms, information and communication technologies in the field, as well as effective scientific achievements it is emphasized that the use and increase of personnel potential (Decree 2019).

State regulation is a more complex process than politics, because it includes the principles of policy development, justification of its rules, selection of means and methods of its implementation (Alekseeva 2022).

In addition, it is necessary to abandon the wrong approach that state policy is one of the elements of state regulation. First, the concept of "state regulation" is often used to describe some measures that reflect the range of political powers and usually play an important role in clarifying the directions, scope and classification of the relevant state policy.

Secondly, "state agrarian policy" used in relation to the agricultural sector may have a somewhat broader description than "state regulation" of the sector, for example, state policy is based on the principles of non-interference of the government in the economic life of society, increasing the effectiveness of state regulation. is more evident in the development of conceptual proposals. At the same time, we should note that the general aspect of state policy measures is that they serve to support agriculture by the state.

The factors identified during the analysis are characterized by a changing description in time and space. This is consistent with our views on the adaptability of the system of state regulation of agriculture to the changing environment.

Yu.V. According to Tkachev and a number of other researchers, agricultural enterprises are characterized by a high susceptibility to agrarian crises compared to other branches and sectors of the economy, and due to the reduction of the scope of government support measures in crisis situations, the activity in the agricultural sector is reduced. Demonstrating enterprises face problems that are difficult to solve (Tkachev et al. 2019).

Analysis and discussion of results. Summarizing the views of economists and industry experts on the specific characteristics and necessity of the state's influence on the economy of the agricultural sector, systematizing the identified factors for its development, justifying the state's measures to support the industry and state allows to develop promising directions for improvement of the regulation system.

In particular, A. V. Agibalov singles out the following main problems faced by the state in the agro-industrial complex, in particular in the field of agricultural support:

- increase in the volume of production of agricultural products aimed at replacing imports and reducing the number of foreign suppliers;

- creation of opportunities to sell products by developing storage, transportation and sales infrastructure;

- increasing capitalization and investment attractiveness, increasing the share of products with high added value aimed at the growth of the processing segment (Musyal and Agibalov 2021).

The above-mentioned problems show that the village is not an isolated sector, it operates in a complex economic system. The efficiency of agriculture largely determines the efficiency of the entire country's economy.

The state can use various forms and methods of influence on certain areas of economic relations in order to solve the assigned tasks.

Turning to the existing experience of developed countries, it allows us to conclude that the modern market does not completely reject state regulation, on the contrary, it exists in various forms and forms. Abandoning the practice of state regulation of agriculture causes a number of problems, such as technological backwardness, the growth of unemployment in rural areas, the growth of food imports, and the increase of threats to food security.

In recent years, there have been certain changes in the priorities for the implementation of reforms in the agrarian sector. Earlier, the state focused on the development of agribusiness, now priority is given to social programs, and it is hoped that this priority will stimulate the development of rural entrepreneurship in the future. The current system of state regulation of agricultural development usually corresponds to the main criteria of economic theory.

Based on the strategy of establishing new economic relations in agriculture and digitalization, the "Agrosubsidy" information system was introduced in order to improve the system of allocating subsidies to agricultural producers in order to financially support the country's agricultural producers. , according to which 22 types of subsidies are planned to be allocated through the electronic platform.

Recognizing that the use of the project-process approach in the system of state regulation of agricultural development is an effective tool, it is recommended to modernize it and adapt it to today's conditions, based on the changing socio-economic conditions. This, in turn, based on the current socio-economic situation, taking into account the issues of ensuring the country's food security, fully solving the problems accumulated in the sector, improving the system of state regulation of the sector, within the country and also , serves to improve the measures aimed at ensuring the competitiveness of agriculture in world markets and to find optimal solutions.

Taking into account the results of a number of researches and proposals for its modernization, the structural scheme of the state regulation of agricultural development in the country is reflected in the diagram below (Fig. 5).

In the course of assessing the current state and gradual progress of the development of the system of state regulation of agricultural development, it can be noted that in the process of market reforms, the mechanism of state regulation changed from the form of direct state financing of the sector to agriculture. gave way to a system that combines crediting and subsidizing economic entities. At the same time, it is more promising to develop a mechanism of state regulation based on the support of lending with the simultaneous development of other financial market institutions with the active use of indirect means of state support and priority development of rural areas. it seems

Despite the development and continuous improvement of the system of state regulation of agricultural development, currently it does not fully correspond to the current situation in

agriculture, does not allow to fully solve the set of problems that have accumulated in the sector. I can conclude that. In addition, the complex geopolitical and geoeconomic processes taking place in the world today have a negative impact on the steady development of agriculture.

It should be noted that the integrated system of agricultural regulation based on market and state principles began to take shape in Uzbekistan in the early 1990s. In addition, it should be taken into account that in most developed countries, agrarian policy has been formed for several decades based on the principles of the socially oriented market, and that developed countries have rich experience in this regard. On the other hand, to study the experience of the formation of systems of regulation of the sector by the state in countries with highly developed agricultural economy, to consider their positive and negative experiences and the prospects of their use in the conditions of Uzbekistan, the development of agriculture in Uzbekistan is a necessary condition for the formation of an effective system of regulation by the state.

In this direction, it is appropriate to use a flexible approach. Direct copying of the foreign experience of state regulation of agricultural development will not give the expected result in local conditions. Due to the specific conditions of agricultural development in Uzbekistan, different aspects of legal regulation, we suggest to apply the rich experience accumulated in the world in the field of agricultural regulation, adapting it to local conditions.

Today, in the agrarian policy in practice in most developed countries, various subsidies, grants and incentives are widely used to support agriculture. In some countries, the amount of state support for agriculture is 1.5-2 times higher than the market value of the industry's products. State support for the development of agriculture and the food industry is now of decisive importance in the rapid growth of food production in the countries that are its main exporters, in particular, the USA, Canada and the European Union. earns (Komar 2019).

In addition, the study of the experience of the countries of the world regarding the regulation of agriculture from the perspective of history and today allows to determine the advantages and disadvantages of different models of state regulation of agriculture. Evaluation, analysis and understanding of this experience will allow to choose the most effective practices, reduce the probability of ineffective solutions, and create a national model of state regulation of agriculture that is somewhat free of errors and shortcomings.

Conclusions and suggestions. The following conclusions were formed within the framework of state regulation of economic relations in the conditions of new economic relations:

1. State regulation of agriculture in order to ensure the stable operation of the agricultural network in the conditions of the dynamic multidirectional influence of the macro, meso and micro environment in the agricultural network represents a complex system of mutually coordinated actions carried out by the state authorities, which affect economic processes, in cooperation with the subjects of the agricultural network.

2. The concepts of "state agrarian policy", "state regulation of agriculture" and "state support" applied to agriculture in practical activities and scientific research related to the field are synonymous in most situations. Intersleeping is used as a concept. This, in turn, is explained by a certain level of similarity of the used tool, mechanism and final goals. Within the framework of this dissertation research, these concepts are addressed in various ways. In our opinion, although these concepts are interrelated, it is appropriate to clarify the differences between them.

3. Classification and clarification of the scope of state support for agriculture is an important element of forming an effective system of state regulation.

4. Possibilities of state support for agriculture collide with the problem of limited budget funds directed to finance the development of the sector. This economic problem implies the identification and selection of the most important directions of state support that will provide the solution to the existing problems in the sector and will give the greatest effect within the framework of the lowest budget costs.

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